

Electromagnetic Work Density Versus Energy and the Photon Wavelength

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Special relativity involves Lorentz transforming energy as the fourth component of a 4-vector. In the case of an electrostatic potential of a charge Q at rest, interacting with a test charge q , also held at rest, potential energy is $q \phi(r)$, where ϕ is the potential in the rest frame. Even though this is a function of an r vector, it represents an energy, i.e. each r vector maps to an energy. The work density in this scenario is $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$ and is not an energy, it is a work density. There is no reason that the work density should transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector, it is not energy. Overall, a charged particle should have a rest mass which includes an intrinsic mass and some contribution from the E field, but it is not clear exactly what this should be.

We note that Gauss' law $\text{grad} \cdot E = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \text{charge density}$ in the rest frame, or $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi$ ((1)) becomes: $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} + 1/(cc) d/dt d/dt \text{partial} \} \phi = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \text{charge density}$ ((2)) in a moving frame. Experimentally, it is known that a hydrogen atom at rest may absorb a photon and transform to an excited state or vice versa. In this scenario, one deals with energy (there is both kinetic and potential), but due to conservation of momentum, there must be overall translational motion, even though it may be very small.

We suggest this implies that a photon is associated with electromagnetic energy (not work density at this point) and that it must be associated with overall translational motion. Thus, one may seek photon solution in ((2)) rather than ((1)). We showed in (1) that such a solution is $\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and $A = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx) (1, 1, 1)$ leading to E, B in a plane perpendicular to motion and to each other.

This solution satisfies $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi + 1/(cc) d/dt d/dt \phi = 0$ because the photon is not linked with charge, even though one has a Q - q interaction. The photon has energy ω and momentum k (as describes a point object, but this energy is now spread throughout space because the electrostatic potential and magnetic vector potential are changed. The solution $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ is also one which exists in space even though the photon is a point. Thus, it seems that there are two representations for the photon, (k, ω) and ϕ, A linked to $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ or the corresponding E, B vectors.

The photon (k, ω) transforms as a 4-vector and represents a point. What then does $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ mean? We investigate this in the note.

EM Energy Versus Work Density

A Lorentz transformation acts on the 4-vector (pc, E) where E is energy. One example is rest mass. If one has an interacting charge system, i.e. a charge Q interacting with q , with both being held fixed, there is an electrostatic potential energy $q \phi$ which is separate from the rest masses associated with Q, q . This energy should transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector. We note that $\phi(r)$ is a function of an r vector, but this simply means that q at different r vector positions represents different energy values. Thus $(0, q \phi(r))$ is a shorthand form of writing many vectors, each for a different r value. It should not be confused for a density.

In addition, the overall Q-q charge system, including its interaction, should represent an overall rest mass which transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector.

There is an additional function with energy units in this scenario, namely the work density:

Work density = $.5 \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r})$ ((3)) “ means rest frame here

This is a density associated with work in creating the charge and is not an energy. There is no reason that a piece of work density should transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector. One may note that for a combined electrostatic -magnetic system at rest, work density is:

Work density = $.5 \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}) + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r})$ ((4))

If a charge at rest has work density given by ((3)) and has E-B fields when moving, one may find ϕ, A (in the moving frame) using $(0, q\phi)$ as the 4-vector transforming into (Ac, ϕ) under a Lorentz transformation. One may then calculate E,B in the moving frame using:

$\mathbf{E} = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ ((4a)) and $\mathbf{B} = \text{grad } \times \mathbf{A}$ ((4b))

Finally, one may calculate ((4)). In the limit, $v \ll c$, one obtains $4/3 (.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}) v$ and not $.5 (.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E})$ as a velocity dependent correction term. This is not a problem, however, because $.5 \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}$ is work density, not energy.

It may be noted that a spherical charged shell in the rest frame becomes a distorted one in the moving frame with a different E distribution as well as B.

The Case of a Photon

A photon seems to be a point-like object which imparts momentum like a particle, but also creates interference/diffraction patterns like a wave. As a point-like object, it should have an energy and momentum which Lorentz transform as a 4-vector. If, further, it has no rest mass, then it should have the dispersion relation:

$E^2 = pc^2 + m^2 c^4 \rightarrow E = pc$ ((5))

((5)) is the relationship for a wave if E is proportional to ω (angular frequency) and p to $k = 2\pi/\text{wavelength}$.

At this point, there is no connection with electromagnetism, but a main source of light in the macroscopic world is the sun (and other stars). Light must be produced in a specific manner. This is known to be due to an excited electron in an atom dropping to a lower energy level, i.e. a quantum process with major impact in the macroscopic world. Thus, light is ultimately connected with electromagnetism as a photon may be emitted or ejected.

To first try to see a photon's connection to electromagnetism, we consider the rest case scenario:

$$-\text{grad dot grad } \phi'' = 1/(4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \epsilon_0) \text{ charge density'' } ((6))$$

The photon is not linked with charge and exhibits wave behaviour and a constant speed when seen from different frames. None of these features is readily evident from ((6)), even with setting $-\text{grad dot grad } \phi''=0$ to find non-charge related potential solutions.

We note that due to conservation of momentum, the absorption or emission of a photon necessarily involves overall translational motion, regardless how small. Thus, it seems that one should seek a photon solution for a moving charge which is described not by ((6)), but by:

$$-\text{grad dot grad } \phi + 1/(c^2) \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } \phi = 1/(4 \cdot 3.14 \cdot \epsilon_0) \text{ charge density } ((7))$$

Such a solution should involve a ϕ piece not linked with charge, i.e. a solution for which the RHS is 0. The motivation for such a solution is the production of light from atoms.

A solution obtained in (1) is:

$$\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx) \text{ and } A = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx) (1,1,1) ((8))$$

This leads to E and B fields perpendicular to each other and the direction of motion if one uses:

$$E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{partial } ((9a)) \text{ and } B = \text{grad } \times A ((9b))$$

((8)), however, seems to lead to an issue. A photon is a point particle with energy $\hbar\omega$ and momentum $\hbar k$. It is not a function of space as is ((8)). An absorbed photon does not change the charge, but changes the energy of a bound charge q . This energy is $q\phi$, i.e. classically the particle moves to a different radius. This means a change in the value of ϕ . Thus, ((8)) is a solution which changes ϕ without changing the charge present. It represents a mapping of a point particle with (k, ω) into points in space in a periodic manner. This is a wavelike pattern, which we argue is linked with experimentally seen interference. Thus, the photon has a dual particle-wave nature as shown in ((8)).

This begs the question: What is the meaning of work density ((4)) given the photon E, and B computed from ((8))?

The Importance of Work Density

Given that work density ((4)) does not transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector, one might be led to believe that this quantity is not important. In principle, one is interested in energies and momentum, not work density. One might argue that it is irrelevant how much energy was needed to assemble a spherical charge. Once it is assembled, one has a corresponding ϕ'' and E'' and that represents all of the necessary physics. Maxwell's equations, however, lead to the expression:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } \{ .5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B \} + 1/\mu_0 \text{grad dot } (E \times B) = E \cdot j ((10))$$

J is current density and is often 0 except for small regions of space. The work density in ((10)) is associated with a dynamic quantity $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$, often called momentum density or the Poynting vector. It seems that one must be careful because there are various momenta in the picture. A charged particle has an overall rest mass including EM effects and a corresponding momentum. A Q-q system has a momentum given by A. Thus, $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ is not the only dynamic quantity in the problem.

We argued that a photon is like a point object $(p, E) = (\hbar k, \hbar \omega)$, but that it is necessarily associated with electromagnetism and so should be linked to E and B fields (i.e. ϕ and A). This association leads to a function in space-time $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$. The photon is not associated with any charge and so $.5 \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}$ is not associated with assembling a charge, but may be associated with the way in which a photon interacts i.e. changes ϕ . In such a case, i.e. focusing on interactions, $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ may have physical meaning as an interacting momentum distribution in space and $.5 \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ as a work density associated with changing the potential energy $q \phi$.

This immediately begs the question: How are the work density and its associated dynamic momentum density $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ (Poynting momentum) linked with (p, E) for a photon? If a photon with energy is absorbed by a q-Q system, its kinetic energy plus potential energy $q \phi$ changes by an amount E . Work, however, is also done in creating this new system and this may be based on some kind of work density and associated momentum density profile. We argue that this may explain what $.5 \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ and $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ represent for a photon. One needs to explicitly calculate the work density and Poynting momentum, say over a wavelength. Given that the solution ((8)) involves $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, one already sees that the result is a function of the point-like energy and momentum $E = \hbar \omega$ and $p = \hbar k$. What is interesting is that the averages of the work density and Poynting vectors are exactly E and p . To see this immediately, in an approximate manner:

$$\text{Integral work density } dx = \text{work} = .5 \epsilon_0 E_0 E_0 \text{ Integral } dx \cos(kx) \cos(kx) \text{ proportional to } k \quad ((11))$$

$w/k=c$ so w is proportional to k and so to w . A similar consideration holds for the integral of $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$.

This leads to the interesting result, that the energy and momentum $\hbar \omega$ and $\hbar k$ of a photon are really related to the kind of work it can do during an interaction. This work is associated with a wavelike structure which manifests itself explicitly during an interaction. Given that one uses the solution $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, w and k are already known, suggesting that $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ may actually be a kind-of probability. In other words, the so-called work density is a work probability density. A photon with momentum k only renders an impulse hit proportional to k , but has an unusual probability profile in space and time given by $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$.

Classically seeking a photon solution for ϕ , A or a moving charge system really involves quantum mechanics which is already present as a photon is produced from an em field in the quantum mechanical manner of light being emitted by a moving atom. We note that one may classically compute light being produced by an accelerating charge, but this scenario may also

be linked to quantum mechanics because unusual $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ fields emerge (namely one proportional to velocity * acceleration) other than one associated with a photon which is proportional to acceleration*acceleration.

The fact that the work density is linked to the probability description of a photon is further enhanced by the notion that one may take the continuity equation ((10)) with 0 on the RHS and “factor” out $\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}$ leaving a quantum wave equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}) (i) + \epsilon_{ijk} \frac{d}{dx_j} (\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}) (k) = 0 \quad ((12))$$

Here ϵ_{ijk} , the Levi Civita symbol, is the spin matrix. For details of this procedure see (2).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a Lorentz transform acts on a 4-vector (pc, E) where E is energy. For two charges, held fixed, the electrostatic interaction energy is $q \phi$, where q is a test charge and Q creates ϕ . Even though this is a function of r vector, each r vector represents an energy value.

It is known that the work done to assemble charges on a conductor and create a magnetic field is: $.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}$, but we argue this represents work density, not energy and should not necessarily transform in a Lorentz transformation. In particular, $.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}$ for a point charge at rest becomes $.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ when seen in a moving frame, but the low velocity $v \ll c$ velocity correction term is $4/3 (.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}) v^2$ and not $.5 (.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}) v^2$.

In (1) we sought a photon solution from $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi + 1/(cc) \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} \phi = 0$ because a photon is physically associated with a q - Q charge system as in the sun. We use the full equation as seen in a moving frame, because due to momentum conservation, the emission or absorption of a photon involves overall translational motion.

This leads to corresponding \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B} fields. We suggest that one may seek such a solution based on the production of light from atoms as in the sun and other stars. The photon is like a point object with $\hbar \omega$ and $\hbar k$ as energy and momentum, but the ϕ solution for no charge source is based on $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, i.e. a function in space which makes use of ω, k .

We suggest that work density and the Poynting vector apply in this case to describe the kind of work a photon can do, i.e. how it can interact in a wavelike manner, but the presence of ω, k in $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ show that this is based on the point-like values ω, k . We suggest that $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ acts like a probability. This quantum type of result already appears in a classical analysis where one seeks a photon-like solution to the generalization of $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \text{charge density}$ in the moving frame, i.e. $-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi + 1/(cc) \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} \phi = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \text{charge density}$ with charge density set to 0. Thus, the photon is associated with a particle-wave duality, with the latter appearing because of its role in electromagnetism, i.e. its solution of a wave equation. In such a case, the work density $.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ and the related Poynting vector are linked to the photon wavefunction $\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}$. In this specific case, the integral of the work density is the photon energy and of $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$, its momentum. The work density, however, has the meaning of a probability.

References

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